

The role of digital technologies in teaching mathematics and programming

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Abstract: This thesis analyses the significance of digitalisation in mathematics and programming education, with a focus on software environments, e-learning platforms, and modern digital technologies. It investigates methods for integrating digital tools into education, including the use of artificial intelligence and big data. The study shows that digital resources expand students' knowledge, improve practical skills, and help teachers manage lessons while encouraging independent and creative learning.

Keywords: Big data, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, electronic libraries.

INTRODUCTION

Today's process of globalisation and rapid technological progress are drastically changing all areas of human life. The process of digitalisation is deeply penetrating not only the economy, manufacturing, the health sector and culture, but also the education system. In particular, the use of information and telecommunication technologies in the modern educational process is of great importance in terms of increasing efficiency, providing students with complex knowledge and expanding the methodological capabilities of teachers¹.

Mathematics and computer science are characterised by complex theoretical foundations, areas of practical application, and tasks requiring logical analysis. The use of digital technologies in teaching these subjects is consequently invaluable for visualising complex concepts, developing students' analytical and creative minds, and effectively organising the learning process.²

In recent years, remote learning platforms, virtual laboratories, electronic libraries, online testing systems, artificial intelligence-based simulators and learning tools have become widely used. With the help of these technologies, students have the opportunity to master the teaching material more deeply and effectively organise the process of independent learning. As a result, the educational process goes outside the traditional framework and becomes more interactive and more creative.

The main objective of this article is to analyse the scientific background of the digitalisation process in mathematics and computer science education, to study existing opportunities and achievements, and to identify areas for further development. In this

regard, the study provides an in-depth scientific analysis of best practices, modern educational techniques, and their impact on the educational process.^{3,4}

METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of this study includes several stages. At the first stage, a systematic analysis of the international and domestic literature and scientific sources on this topic was carried out. In scientific articles, abstracts of international conferences and monographs that were published in recent years, the use of digital educational tools and their theoretical and practical foundations were studied in depth. This phase served to form the conceptual basis of the study.

The second stage analysed digital tools actively used in the educational process. In particular, the advantages and limitations of software packages such as GeoGebra, MATLAB, and WolframAlpha, which are widely used in mathematics teaching, were studied. In the field of computer science and computer programming, the practical effectiveness of Python, C++, Scratch, and the online IDE (Integrated Development Environment) was evaluated.

During the study, the outcomes of traditional and digital learning were compared using a comparative method. The statistical analysis was based on pedagogical observations with students. In particular, the results of two groups of students were checked using Student's t -test:

$$t = \frac{x_1 - x_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

where x_1, x_2 - mean values of both groups, s_1^2, s_2^2 - dispersions, n_1, n_2 - number of observations.

To assess the results more reliably, the correlation coefficient was calculated:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \cdot \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

These formulas were used to determine the correlation between the level of digital educational tool usage and students' knowledge indicators.

During the experimental sessions, approaches such as remote learning, blended learning, gamification, and adaptive learning were implemented. The performance of each model was evaluated based on student motivation dynamics, students' independent learning skills, and their interest in the subject.

Thus, the research was based not only on the analysis of theoretical literature, but also on the treatment of empirical data using statistical methods, as well as on findings based on mathematical calculations.

RESULTS

The study conducted has virtually proven the effectiveness of digital learning tools. Students who worked with interactive technologies in mathematics were able to

solve complex problems faster and more accurately. For another example, when solving differential equations using MATLAB, students obtained results on average 40% faster than when using conventional calculation methods. In addition, demonstrating geometric figures using GeoGebra significantly increased students' understanding of the subject.⁵

In computer science, the use of programming instruments played a major role in shaping algorithmic thinking among students. For example, the use of interactive mediums such as Jupyter Notebook in the process of learning Python has allowed students to see the results of their code in real time. This has accelerated the practical application of theoretical knowledge. For primary school students, visual media such as Scratch served as an effective tool for increasing interest in programming.

Statistical results showed that the level of knowledge acquisition in groups using digital tools was on average 20-30% higher. In addition, a substantial increase in student motivation to learn was noted. These results prove the effectiveness of digitalisation in the educational process with evidence based on scientific research.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of digital technologies in teaching science and mathematics, in particular mathematics and computer science, considerably increases the effectiveness of the educational process. Modern modern digital tools not only allow for the quick and effective transfer of knowledge, but also serve to improve understanding of complex concepts and develop students' creative and logical thinking. At the same time such tools increase the potential for independent work by students, create opportunities for the use of a wide range of media sources, and adapt the educational process to modern requirements.

Therefore, further digitalisation of the education system, improvement of technical infrastructure, enhancement of teachers' digital skills, and widespread introduction of new and innovative new technologies will remain pressing issues in the future.

References

1. Redecker, C., & Punie, Y. (2017). European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators: DigCompEdu. Publications Office of the European Union.
2. Voogt, J., & Knezek, G. (2018). Teaching and learning in the digital age: Research on ICT integration in education. Springer.
3. Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017–1054.
4. Zawacki-Richter, O., & Latchem, C. (2018). Exploring four decades of research in Computers & Education. *Computers & Education*, 122, 136–152.
5. Naser M. A. M. Alkandari & Meshael K. Abushiebah. Effects of Using MATLAB in Improving Students' Skills in Mathematics. *Journal of Research in Applied Mathematics*, Vol. 10, Issue 5 (2024).